

Royal Society

Data management plan required?	Yes
RDM policy Link	No
Definition of data	Useful data or datasets that have arisen from the research that we support. Computational or curated data produced by an experimental or observational procedure.
Length of data management plan	Maximum of 200 words
DMP template/ requirements	No set format, but should highlight: What data outputs will be generated by the research that are of value to the public? Where and when will you make the data available? How will others be able to access the data? If data is of high public interest, how will it be made available to a wider public audience? Any constraints (legal, ethical, commercial) How will data sets be preserved for them to be of long-term benefit?
Required data repository	None specified, but data should be archived in an 'appropriate and openly available' repository
Time for data release	Not specified
Time for long-term storage of data	Not specified
Costings	Not specified
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	grants@royalsociety.org
Comments	Sir Henry Dale Fellowships have adopted Wellcome Trust policies on data management and data sharing. (See Wellcome Trust)

Documents used:

Grant schemes conditions of award:

<https://royalsociety.org/~media/grants-schemes-awards/grants/Apex%20Awards/2017-award-holders/Conditions%20of%20Award.pdf>

Dorothy Hodgkins Fellowship Scheme Notes (Also Research grant scheme notes)

<https://royalsociety.org/~media/grants/schemes/DHF-scheme-notes.pdf>

Accessed: May 2018